

DENOTATIVE AND CONNOTATIVE MEANINGS IN WORD SEMANTICS

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Abstract: This article covers the issues of comparative analysis of denotative and connotative meanings in English and Uzbek languages in word semantics. Comparative study of connotative meaning in linguistics, delimitation of denotative and connotative meanings, determining the place and value of language tools in the realization of these meanings in speech has become the object of scientific work in the current period. The realization of connotative meaning, its inherent and adherent forms in the speech process has different character and characteristics.

Keywords: denotation, connotation, communicative, expressive, inherent, adherent, stylistic, emotive evaluation, pragmatic meaning, denotative, connotative, nominative, meaning shade, differentiation, contextual meaning, paradigmatic series, dominant, stylistic color.

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The fact that language is a tool that can perform nominative, communicative and expressive functions, the internal dualism of language - on the one hand, it is a form of thinking that reflects an objective existence, and on the other hand, the essence of each element is an independent system arising from the internal relations of this element with other elements.

If the nominative function of the language is related to the fact that its form of thinking is a tool that shapes concepts, then its expressive function is related to the fact that the language is an independent system, the essence of elements can be revealed only from their internal relations.

The fact that the language has nominative and expressive functions must be reflected in the elements of the language, especially in the word. Because the word is the main unit of the lexicon and grammar, which are the main levels of the language. In this article, we will consider denotative and connotative meanings in word semantics. In fact, all linguists note that the word has two different meanings: (denotative) name, naming and additional emotional-expressive (connotative) meaning. The additional meaning of the word is called by different names in linguistics, such as "stylistic coloring", "expressive meaning ottenka", "additional meaning" (soznachenie). Underlying these designations are the terms denotation and connotation.

There are scientifically based opinions devoted to the denotative meaning of the word, the place of the denotative meaning in the speech process, because the

denotative meaning is the main function of the word. But in the speech, there are connotative meanings that give different shades of additional meaning to the denotative meaning, and if one feature is expressed in a certain context, another edge can be found in another context. In the scientific literature, it is noted that connotation is the expression of the connotative meaning of the language unit attached to the denotation, and the additional symbols surrounding it.

Connotation is a semantic entity included in the semantics of language units, and it expresses the emotive evaluation and methodologically determined attitude of the subject of speech to existence. In the further development of linguistics, interest in the connotative aspect of linguistic units has increased, but the concept of connotation is interpreted differently in different disciplines. In particular, in stylistics, connotation is considered as a stylistic meaning, and it is studied with emotional coloring. In translation studies, connotation is viewed as a pragmatic meaning, and semasiologists who study meaning in a systematic aspect view connotation as an expressive color, an emotional expression. In psychological studies, connotation is approached as semantic associations. No matter how this term is assessed, its main function is the function of influence, which is directly and continuously connected with the pragmatics of speech.

When studying the structure of word semantics, there are two types of connotation: inherent (the connotative meaning inherent in a word when it is taken out of context), adherent connotation (the connotative meaning that is formed in a word in a certain context).

We give the following examples of how the internal connotative meaning can or cannot be a part of the semantics of a word: Analyzing the adjective "*beautiful*" in the English language, its synonymous line, *beautiful* is neutral (or dominant), its synonyms: *pretty, attractive, lovely...* are words with additional colors. For example: *she was beautiful girl so we need. - But not beautiful, she was so attractive, I mean.*

The fact that the word has denotative and connotative meanings determines that the word is one of the main tools of artistic representation. Any connotative expressions contain certain symbols characteristic of the denotative meaning. The speaker refers to this sema (sign) when expressing a pragmatic purpose. For this reason, the subject of denotation performs two functions: evaluation and understanding.

The subject of connotation performs three tasks: understanding, pure evaluation, emotive classification, that is, a task related to personal pragmatic activity. Thus, in addition to the denotative meaning, the word semantics also has a connotative meaning, which is found at all language levels (lexical, phonetic, morphological, syntactic).

Analyzing the synonyms such as terrible, dreadful, horrible, horrid, terrible is a neutral word, i.e. dominant, and its synonyms express a strong negative color compared to terrible. Compared to the word terrible, horrid has a more negative meaning, that is, it expresses additional meanings such as vile, disgusting. Also, from a lexical point of view, additional meanings such as strengthening and happiness are formed in the synonymy of some words. Therefore, not only the additional meaning in these words, but also certain intonation features are determined by the laws of the language, these are elements of the language, and they are a reflection of the expressive function of the language in words. Since such additional (connotative) meanings are related to the context, determined by the language, they are considered as components of the semantic structure of the word, that is, they are a language element and are included in the semantics of the word.

Therefore, the language performs its communicative function in the dialectic unity of nominative and expressive functions. In scientific literature, the expressive function of language is relegated to the background, while in fiction, the expressive function of language plays a decisive role. The word has denotative and connotative meanings related to both the nominative and expressive functions of the language. The fact that the word has denotative and connotative meanings determines that the word is one of the main tools of the artistic image. If the connotative meaning of the word is included in the semantic structure of the word, then this word will certainly take a place in a certain synonymous line. The artistic skill of the writer depends on the art of using these synonyms correctly and with increasing their effectiveness as much as possible. But the feature that makes the word one of the important tools of artistic speech is its ability to have a speech connotative meaning.

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